

**STUDIES IN ORGANO ARSENIC COMPOUNDS. PART VI.
SYNTHESIS OF 1-CHLOROARSINDOLE FROM
CINNAMIC ACID.**

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The present investigation is an attempt to synthesise 1-chloroarsindole by the conversion of *o*-aminocinnamic acid and its ethyl ester into the corresponding arsonic acid which may then be transformed into arsindole by Fischer's method. *o*-Aminocinnamic acid by Bart's reaction gave a tri-derivative (cf. Goswami and Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 417) which could not be converted into the corresponding indole derivative under usual conditions. Ethyl *o*-aminocinnamate, however, gave a primary arsonic acid (I) in good yield which can be easily hydrolysed to cinnamic-*o*-arsonic acid (II), but the latter does not give arsindole by Fischer's method. In acetic acid solution (II) reacts with hydrogen bromide to give β -bromohydrocinnamic-*o*-arsonic acid (III). When treated with dilute sodium carbonate the arsonic acid is converted into styrolene-*o*-arsonic acid (IV) (cf. Basler, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 596, 1494). Reduction of the styrolene compound with sulphur dioxide in hydrochloric acid solution gives styrolene-*o*-arsenious chloride (V), which by Friedel-Crafts' reaction gives 1-chloroarsindole (VI), identified by the formation of mercuric chloride double compound and the picrate and also mixed m.p. with a sample prepared from β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine (Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 349).

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

tris-o-(β-Carboxyvinyl)-phenylarsonic Oxide or tris-Cinnamic-o-arsenic Oxide, $(C_6H_4 \cdot CH=CH \cdot COOH)_3AsO$.—The diazo solution from *o*-aminocinnamic acid (5 g.) was added gradually to a well cooled and mechanically stirred mixture of sodium carbonate (12 g.), arsenious acid (4 g.), copper sulphate (15 g.) and water (40 c. c.). The resulting dark brown solution was filtered, concentrated to a low bulk, cooled and filtered again. The filtrate was just acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitated dark brown solid was purified from alcohol as yellow amorphous solid not melting up to 300°. [Found: C, 60·1; H, 3·6; As, 13·8. $C_{27}H_{31}O_7As$ requires C, 60·9; H, 3·9; As, 14·3 per cent].

o-(β-Carbethoxyvinyl)-phenylarsonic Acid (I).—To mechanically stirred and cooled solution of anhydrous sodium carbonate (75 g.), arsenious oxide (30 g.), copper sulphate (1 g.) and water (150 c. c.), the diazo solution prepared from *o*-aminocinnamic ester (15 g.), hydrochloric acid (24 c. c.), water (50 c. c.) and sodium nitrite (9 g.) was added. Too much frothing occurred but this was controlled by increasing the speed of rotation of the stirrer. The solution was stirred for 1 hour more and allowed to remain overnight, filtered and one third of the filtrate was taken and the acid was precipitated by concentrated hydrochloric acid avoiding excess. The precipitated dull yellow solid was separated, dried, and then purified three times from methyl alcohol and ether. It is a brownish yellow product sintering at 175° but not melting up to 360°. [Found: C, 43·8; H, 4·1; As, 25·2. $C_{11}H_9O_5As$ requires C, 44·0; H, 4·3; As, 25·0 per cent].

o-(β-Carboxyvinyl)-phenylarsonic Acid (II).—The remaining filtrate from the above procedure was first heated under reflux to hydrolyse the ester and then concentrated to a low bulk, cooled and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a dull yellow mass. This was crystallised from methyl alcohol and ether as golden yellow amorphous powder, m. p. 205·6°. The acid is readily soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, and hot nitrobenzene, moderately soluble in water and chloroform and insoluble in benzene, ether, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride. (Found: C, 39·8; H, 2·9; As, 27·4. $C_9H_9O_5As$ requires C, 39·7; H, 3·3; As 27·5 per cent.).

β-Bromohydrocinnamic-o-arsonic Acid (III)—*o*-(β-Carboxyvinyl)-phenylarsonic acid (7 g.) and glacial acetic acid (50 c. c.), saturated at 0° with anhydrous hydrogen bromide, were heated in a sealed tube at 100° for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour and the pressure released at once with a view to prevent the action of excess of hydrogen bromide on the addition

product. The reaction mixture was heated for 10 minutes on a water-bath and diluted with water in the cold; the yellow product separating was taken up in chloroform, filtered and precipitated by ether. It was then crystallised from dilute acetic acid as a yellow compound, m.p. 185°. (Found: Br, 21.9; As, 21.2. $C_9H_{10}O_3BrAs$ requires Br, 22.6; As, 21.2 per cent). It is soluble in alcohol, chloroform and acetic acid; sparingly soluble in benzene, carbon disulphide, and insoluble in ether and carbon tetrachloride.

Styrolene-o-arsonic Acid (IV).— β -Bromohydrocinnamic-o-arsonic acid was heated under reflux with a solution of sodium carbonate (5% excess of theoretical quantity) for 1 hour, filtered and then acidified after cooling. A yellow precipitate was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol as a yellow powder, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 41.8; H, 3.8; As, 32.7. $C_9H_9O_3As$ requires C, 42.1; H, 3.9; As, 32.8 per cent).

Styrolene-o-arsenious Chloride (V).—Styrolene-o-arsonic acid was dissolved in alcohol and excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. The solution was first warmed and then saturated with sulphur dioxide for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour in the presence of a crystal of potassium iodide. The major portion of the alcohol was removed and the residue dried on a porous plate and then crystallised from carbon disulphide as a yellow amorphous powder, m.p. 55°. (Found: C, 38.2; H, 2.6; Cl, 28.4; As, 30.1. $C_9H_7Cl_2As$ requires C, 38.5; H, 2.8; Cl, 28.5; As, 30.1 per cent).

1-Chloroarsindole (VI).—Styrolene-o-arsenious chloride (7 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) in absolute carbon disulphide (300 c.c.) were heated under reflux. The heating was continued for about 5 hours. The mass was decomposed by ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted several times with carbon disulphide. The extract was of brown colour and contained a brownish violet solid giving fluorescence in alcohol. It was filtered and the solvent evaporated off in an inert atmosphere. The residual brown oil, having a very painful penetrating odour was distilled in *vacuo* at 125-30°/5 mm. The colour of the yellow oil became dark on keeping. The mercuric chloride addition product of its methyl derivative melted at 151° and was found to be identical with that described before (Das-Gupta, *loc. cit.*). (Found: Cl, 16.5; As, 35.1. C_8H_8ClAs requires Cl, 16.7; As, 35.2 per cent).

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